

Highly-doped optical fibers for high-efficiency holmium lasers

M. Kamrádek*, I. Kašík, J. Aubrecht, P. Vařák, O. Podrazký, I. Bartoň, P. Peterka, P. Honzátko
Institute of Photonics and Electronics, Czech Academy of Sciences, Chaberská 57, 182 00 Praha,
Czech Republic

ABSTRACT

Optical fibers highly-doped with aluminum oxide and holmium ions for a use in fiber lasers were prepared and tested in a laser arrangement. The fibers were prepared using modified chemical vapor deposition method in combination with nanoparticle-doping method. Relations between fibers composition and their laser parameters were studied within a series of various Al_2O_3 and Ho^{3+} concentrations. Fibers with fluorescence lifetime above 1.5 ms were prepared and lasers with slope efficiency up to 86% and laser threshold below 50 mW were constructed. Molar ratio Al/Ho equals to at least 50 was found to be the key factor for fibers with such excellent parameters. Thanks to high concentrations of Al_2O_3 (up to 10 mol.%), enabled by nanoparticle doping, we achieved high performance in a wide range of Ho^{3+} concentrations (1000–6000 ppm). The results will be used in the designing of highly-efficient high-power cladding-pumped holmium fiber lasers.

Keywords: optical fibers, fiber lasers, holmium, MCVD

1. INTRODUCTION

Silica-based holmium-doped optical fibers are widely studied for their emission around 2.1 μm [1, 2]. Such fibers can be conveniently prepared by modified chemical vapor deposition (MCVD) method in combination with additional techniques such as solution doping, nanoparticle doping or vapor phase chelate delivery [3]. To minimize clustering of Ho^{3+} ions, the fibers are usually co-doped with aluminum oxide [4, 5]. In 2019, we found a strong dependence of fluorescence lifetime and laser parameters on fiber composition [6]. The fibers were of low and moderate level of doping; they contained up to 4 mol.% of Al_2O_3 and 3000 ppm of Ho^{3+} . An improvement was reported in 2020 [7].

In this paper, we follow up on our previous works by increasing the dopant concentrations up to 10 mol.% of Al_2O_3 and 6000 ppm of Ho^{3+} , and we present highly-doped holmium silica-based optical fibers optimized for fiber lasers. A special emphasis is placed on compositions with high Al/Ho ratio to obtain fluorescence lifetime longer than 1 ms, laser threshold below 100 mW and laser slope efficiency above 75%.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation and characterization of preforms and optical fibers

Optical preforms were fabricated through the MCVD process [8]. Fused silica tubes (F300, Heraeus) served as substrates. Silicon tetrachloride (Siridion STC 100, Evonik) and onsite purified oxygen (dew point <-99.9 °C) were used as SiO_2 precursors. At first, the deposition tube was polished above 2000 °C and two pure SiO_2 layers were deposited as buffer layers. Thereafter, a frit (porous core layer) was deposited. The frit was subsequently soaked with a doping suspension containing aluminum oxide nanoparticles ($\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, 99.9%, Merck) and holmium (III) chloride ($\text{HoCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.99%, Merck) in absolute ethanol. After drying, the frit was sintered under a chlorine atmosphere and collapsed into a rod. Finally, standard single-mode fibers were drawn and coated with a UV-curable acrylate (Cablelite 3471-3-14).

Preform homogeneity was verified by measuring refractive index profiles using an A2600 profiler (Photon Kinetics). Concentration profiles of Al_2O_3 in preforms were obtained by electron probe microanalysis using a JXA-8230 analyzer (Jeol). Ho^{3+} concentration in fibers was evaluated based on absorption at 1950 nm. Fluorescence lifetimes were measured using a diode emitting at 1150 nm (Innolume FBF-1150-PM-300) and a Hamamatsu G8371-01 InGaAs PIN photodiode as a detector; detailed description can be found elsewhere [9]. Laser parameters of the fibers were tested in a Fabry-Perot configuration. The holmium-doped fiber laser was formed by a highly reflective fiber Bragg grating (R~99.5% at 2100 nm) and a cleaved fiber end. Thulium-doped fiber laser with maximum output power of 1 W at 1950 nm was used as a pumping source.

*kamradek@ufe.cz

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Relevant parameters of the tested fibers are listed in Table 1, and the relations between fibers composition and parameters studied are depicted as a form of 3D graphs in Figs. 1-3.

Table 1. Relevant parameters of fibers under study.

Sample	Al ₂ O ₃ (mol.%)	Ho ³⁺ (mol. ppm)	Abs. @ 1950 nm (dB/m)	Al/Ho	Fluorescence lifetime (μs)	Slope (%)	Threshold (mW)
1	10.0	2820	79.6	71	1488	79.4	91
2	8.8	6143	173.9	29	1190	63.6	208
3	8.8	5705	161.5	31	1200	70.3	156
4	10.4	1300	35.5	160	1610	86.2	47
5	10.3	2600	71.5	80	1470	80.9	57
6	10.6	2200	60.8	96	1510	78.4	70
7	10.3	1300	36.5	158	1560	78.0	49
8	9.8	1480	40.9	133	1460	85.5	59
9	9.1	2300	64.1	79	1391	81.2	80
10	9.3	2850	80.1	66	1350	79.9	80
11	9.4	3500	98.0	54	1312	77.8	86
12	9.4	3850	107.9	49	1247	78.5	84
13	9.3	1900	53.1	98	1370	81.1	76
14	10.0	5150	144.7	39	1260	74.6	94

The dependence of fluorescence lifetime on Ho³⁺ concentration and Al/Ho ratio is depicted in Fig. 1. Lifetimes 1.2–1.6 ms obtained in a broad range of Ho³⁺ concentrations are a sign of overall high quality of the fibers.

Fig. 1. Fluorescence lifetime as a function of Ho³⁺ concentration and Al/Ho molar ratio.

Laser slope efficiency as a function of Ho^{3+} concentration and Al/Ho ratio can be found in Fig. 2. The best-performance fibers exhibited slope efficiency above 85%. For high efficiencies (around 80%), the Al/Ho ratio needs to be at least 50. Thus, for high-efficiency fibers with Ho^{3+} concentration above 4000 ppm, it would be necessary to increase the Al_2O_3 content above 10 mol.%.

Fig. 2. Laser slope efficiency as a function of Ho^{3+} concentration and Al/Ho molar ratio.

The dependence of laser threshold on Ho^{3+} and Al/Ho ratio can be found in Fig. 3. Generally, quite low values of laser threshold were obtained, and fibers with Al/Ho ratio higher than 50 exhibited thresholds below 100 mW.

Fig. 3. Laser threshold as a function of Ho^{3+} concentration and Al/Ho molar ratio.

Based on the measured data, we can say the best-performance fibers need to have Al/Ho molar ratio at least 50. Thanks to high Al₂O₃ content, attained by nanoparticle-doping method, we were able to keep this ratio in a broad Ho³⁺ concentration range from 1000 ppm to almost 4000 ppm. More details and explanations can be found also in our recently published paper [10]. Data supporting the results can be found in [11].

4. CONCLUSIONS

A series of 14 fibers highly-doped with Al₂O₃ and Ho³⁺ optimized for fiber lasers was presented. The fibers were prepared by MCVD combined with nanoparticle-doping technique and contained up to 10 mol.% of Al₂O₃ and about 6000 ppm of Ho³⁺. Relations between fibers composition and their fluorescence lifetime and laser parameters were studied; it was proven Al/Ho molar ratio has a strong effect on the parameters studied. For high-performance fibers, the Al/Ho ratio needs to be greater than 50. Such fibers can reach outstanding parameters – fluorescence lifetime longer than 1.5 ms, slope efficiency above 80% and laser threshold below 100 mW. The nanoparticle doping was found a suitable method for preparation of highly-doped and highly-efficient holmium fibers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was co-funded by the European Union and the state budget of the Czech Republic under the project LasApp CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004573. This work was supported by Czech Science Foundation (23-05701S).

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